

OPTIMIZATION AND ASSESMENT OF FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES AS WELL AS COOKING PARAMETERS OF READY TO COOK KODO MILLET NOODLE

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(MS Received: 13.08.2023; MS Revised:06.10.2023; MS Accepted:07.10.2023)

MS 3114

(RESEARCH PAPER IN FOOD PROCESSING AND TECHNOLOGY,)

Abstract

Kodo millet is categorised as coarse grain and is mainly grown in India, China, Japan, Russia and Africa. It comprises protein 8.35%, carbohydrate 65.65%, ash 2.95% and fat 1.45%. It is regarded as cereal nutrient. After coming across this nutritionally rich millet and realizing the growing demand for convenient ready to cook food which will not only be good in taste but will have great nutritional as well as health benefits, we directed our work in the development of this Ready to cook kodo millet noodle, that will be convenient to cook and will act as a functional food, as kodo is well known for its various therapeutic properties like- it is easy to digest due to higher amount of lecithin which is good for nervous system, it is gluten free thus most suitable for individuals intolerant to gluten, useful in treating asthma, blood pressure, migrane, diabetic heart diseases etc.

In this study the Ready to cook kodo millet noodles were standardised in three different proportions of kodo millet flour and corn starch (75:25, 80:20, 85:15) and its functional properties (swelling power, solubility index and water absorbance), cooking parameters (optimal cooking time, cooking loss, breakage %, water absorbance) were measured.

Key Words- Kodo, millet, ready to cook noodle, functional property, cooking parameters.

Introduction-

Millets are the member from grass family and native of Africa and Asia. Kodo millet is probably started in South-East Asia (Ghimire et al., 2017). A yearly grass variety develops around 90 cm level. It is monocot crop and more modest size seeds, 1.5 mm in width, 2 mm long. The kodo millet grain variety shifts from light red to dim dark which is limited in extreme husk that is hard to eliminate. Kodo millet is categorized a coarse grain (Bunkar et al., 2021). Millets are critical natural food security crops known for their quality and need no assets for their growth (Joshi et al., 2008). Kodo (*paspalum scrobiculatum*) is one among of the six other minor millets. It takes a longer duration to mature, for example four to a half year differentiated and various millets that expects two to four months. Kodo millet is broadly grown on the poorest of soils (IIMR, 2016). It can sustain drought condition crop and have long storage period without insect damage (Adekunle, 2012). Kodo millet also known as koden, kodra in hindi; varagu in tamil; arika, arikelu in telugu; harka in kannada; kodra in gujarati, marathi, punjabi; kodua in oriya.

Maize also called as corn, is a cereal grain first cultivated by native indigenous in Southern Mexico about 10,000 years ago (Benz, 2001) The grain yield of maize depends on the genetic potential of the genotype used, the characteristics of the soil, the field management practices and agro climatic factors. (Tandzi et al., 2020). The parts of yellow dent corn are the going with, it is basically made out of starch, at 62%.

Extruded product were among the most commercially successful extruded food varieties. Extrusion cooking is the process broadly utilized for the development of snacks which are mainly manufactured from cereal flour or starches. Extruded products are normally high in calories and fat with low satisfied of protein, fiber, and saw as unfortunate food to numerous consumers (Larrea et al., 2005; Wandee et al., 2014). Noodles are one of the well-known food sources in many parts of the Asian nations (Bangladesh, India, China, Japan, Thailand, and so on) for its high wholesome quality and for having agreeable flavor. Also, it is prepared to eat food, savvy and profoundly accessible. In any case, locally accessible noodles are not healthfully rich as it is predominantly ready from wheat. Wheat isn't considered as a good source of nutrients, as it is not a source of complete protein (Horigane et al., 2004),

Material And Methods**Description of Noodles Maker-**

The laboratory model of cold press noodles maker was a small, compact, cold extruder. The unit has single screw extruder with a short screw of uniform pitch powered by 1hp electrical motor.

Treatment	Kodo millet flour	Corn starch
N-1	75	25
N-2	80	20
N-3	85	15

Procurement of the raw materials-

Kodo millet and other ingredients were procured from local market of Prayagraj city for the development of ready to cook Kodo based noodles. With the variation of kodo millet flour and other ingredients product was standardised.

Treatment table-

N-1- kodo noodle prepared with composition (75:25) of kodo millet flour and corn starch.

N-2 kodo noodle prepared with composition (80:20) of kodo millet flour and corn starch.

N-3 kodo noodle prepared with composition (85:15) of kodo millet flour and corn starch.

Treatment combinations for prepared ready to cook kodo noodles-**Development of the ready to cook kodo based noodles-**

Kodo flour and corn starch were mixed in three proportions of 75:25 ; 80:20 and 85:15 to prepare noodles of three different composition and additives like salt, kansui (potassium carbonate and sodium carbonate) were separately dissolved in known amount of water and this solution was added to flour to make crumbly dough by proper kneading and then kept to rest for 30 min. then the noodles were extruded using cold press extruder there after these noodles were immediately steam cooked in autoclave, strained kept in running ice water to stop any further cooking and dried in hot air oven at 50° C for 2 hr.

Fig.01 ready to cook kodo millet noodle

Fig.02 flow chart representing development of ready to cook kodo millet noodle.

Cooking quality of kodo based noodles-

Cooking quality of noodles is the most important quality

Cooking time

5gm of noodle samples was put in a beaker with measured amount of distilled water and cooked properly. The noodle strand was checked properly till the core had no white fractions using glass slides.

ready to cook kodo based noodles

Cooking loss

It was measured by calculating the solid substance loss in the water. The water after cooking was poured in the pre weighed beaker and

Results and discussion

Cooking parameters of noodles-

S.No.	Sample	OCT (min)	Cooking loss(%)	Water abs(%)	Breakage (%)
1	N-1	7	19.23	16.56	24.85
2	N-2	8	20.84	15.46	35
3	N-3	8	28.24	12.34	53.15

Fig.03 graph representing cooking parameters of prepared noodles.

Cooking parameters were checked for noodles and are mentioned in the above table. Here represents optimal cooking time which was found in kodo noodle it was about 7-8 minutes. The noodles were checked properly till the core had no white fractions using glass slides.

The percentage of cooking loss and breakage was found to be increasing with the decrease in the starch content in the composition of kodo noodle, so the maximum cooking loss was found in N-3 it was 28.24% and least was in N-1 19.23%, likewise breakage % was also maximum in N-3 53.15% and least in N-1 24.85%. But in the case for water absorption when the starch is decreasing the capacity of water absorbance is also decreasing respectively.

evaporated, then dried in oven completely and weighed again. The dry residue was weighed and loss percentage was calculated.

Breakage percentage

Initially the number of noodle strands in 10gm samples were counted and after cooking again the non-broken and broken strands were counted. Finally, by subtracting the no. of broken strands from the no. of total strands, breakage percentage was obtained.

Water uptake

It was estimated by calculating difference in the final and initial weight of noodles before and after cooking.

Functional Properties-

Swelling power-

swelling power of noodles is performed by schoch (1964), a known weight of noodles was cooked in a glass beaker with then times of quantity of boiling water (100 ml) for 5 by the method of water bath system maintained at 100°C. After cooking the water strained out and the cooked pasta was dried to remove the surface moisture using the filter paper and the cooked sample was weighed. from the initial weight of noodles swelling power was calculated as-

$$\text{Swelling power} \left(\frac{g}{g} \right) = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1}$$

Where

W₁ - Initial sample weight before cooking (g)

W₂ - Sample weight after cooking (g).

Solubility Power

Weigh and label clean petri plates. Take 10 ml of the supernatant in each of them. Put the Petri plates on water bath for evaporation. Once evaporated completely, put them into oven for drying (70-80° C). Cool them in a desiccator and once cooled, weigh them.

Calculation

$$\text{Water Solubility Index} = \frac{\text{weight of dry residue (mg)} \times 2.5 \times 100}{\text{weight of the sample}}$$

Where, 2.5 is balance factor

Swelling and Solubility power-swelling power

Sample	30 °C	50°C	70°C	90°C
N-1	3.56 ± 0.03	3.78 ± 0.09	4.68 ± 0.02	5.03 ± 0.06
N-2	4.67 ± 0.26	3.69 ± 0.23	4.41 ± 0.21	5.19 ± 0.13
N-3	4.76 ± 0.03	5.02 ± .067	5.36 ± 0.56	6.69 ± 0.39

Fig.04 graph representing swelling power of prepared noodles.

Solubility-power

Sample	30 °C	50°C	70°C	90°C
N-1	3.01 ± 1.48	8.00 ± 2.62	8.12 ± 0.04	10.44 ± 0.28
N-2	3.67 ± 0.45	8.11 ± 1.33	8.42 ± 0.26	11.74 ± 2.42
N-3	3.98 ± 0.66	9.44 ± 1.02	9.64 ± 0.72	11.90 ± 1.05

Fig.05 graph representing solubility power of prepared noodles.

The swelling power of the noodles was seen to be increasing with the increase in the temperature. The lowest was observed at 30°C and highest at 90°C.

For solubility also similar pattern of increasing order was observed. For noodle N-3 maximum value was shown by 11.90 ± 1.05 .

Si. No.	Sample	WA%
1	N-1	34.56 ± 2.25
2	N-2	31.9 ± 2.12
3	N-3	28.9 ± 2.95

Water Absorption-

Water absorption index for N-1 was found to be highest it was $34.56 \pm 2.25\%$ and a further decrease in the WAI was observed in N-2 with $31.9 \pm 2.12\%$ and in N-3 $28.9 \pm 2.95\%$. WAI for noodles were found to be less since kodo millet is gluten free, thus able to bind less water

Conclusion

Kodo millet is a cereal nutrient, rich in nutrient profile, good source of protein, carbohydrate and energy. It is gluten free making it more suitable for people having gluten intolerance.

Our work was aimed in developing noodle using kodo millet flour blended with corn starch as there are several kodo noodles available in market but have equal or greater quantity of wheat flour, so to overcome this we developed noodle using major amount of kodo and no amount of wheat flour was used, making it completely gluten free. We tested our prepared noodle for various cooking parameter and observed that noodle having greater amount of starch, N-1 (75:25) has less cooking loss as well as breakage % than those having lesser starch content N-2 (80:20) and N-3 (85:15) and water absorbance of N-1 (16.56) was found to be greater than N-2 (15.46) and N-3 (12.34). These means greater the starch amount gives the noodle good water absorbance resulting in less loss during cooking.

The prepared noodles were also tested on functional parameters like swelling power and solubility index. The swelling power of the noodles was seen to be increasing with the increase in the temperature. The lowest was observed at 30°C and highest at 90°C.

For solubility also similar pattern of increasing order was observed. For noodle N-3 maximum value was shown by 11.90 ± 1.05 .

Though there is some further scope of improvement in Ready to cook kodo millet noodles in terms of cooking parameters but it was found to be superior nutritionally than other commercially available kodo noodles blended with greater amount of wheat flour.

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